

Rājavinoda Mahākāvyaṃ

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Editorial

First draft of this paper was in Urdu and received for Pratnakirti (vol. 3, issue 1), but due to some technical difficulties related to Latex we could not published it in that very issue. The Urdu version of the paper has appeared in Daryaft (issue 26) published by the National University of Modern languages, Islamabad. We are thankful to Professor Hashmi to send this article again in English.

Abstract

It is often believed the Sanskrit language declined during the reign of Muslim kings or sultans because they did not give it adequate attention. There have occasionally been published research findings that support this notion as well as others that are opposed to it or deny it.

Sultan Mahmud Shah I of Gujarat is the subject of numerous contradictory accounts in historical records. Some claims and arguments regarding him are refuted by recent studies. One of the most significant factors that have been taken into account is the fact that he was not only a lover of Sanskrit literature and language, but also a patron of the language. In his court, a Sanskrit poet had the title of Malek-ush-Sho'ara (Poet Laureate), and his seminal work in Sanskrit Rajvinod Mahakavyam recounts the history of the Gujarati sultans with particular attention to Mahmud.

With the splendor of the sociopolitical facets of Mahmud Shah I's rule, the poet has masterfully woven the entirety of his age's history into this artistic tapestry. This poem is a good choice to use as a representative illustration of the patronage of Sanskrit by Muslim rulers. This epic depicts the popularity of the Sultan among his subjects in addition to incorporating Arabic and Persian terms into Sanskrit with beauty and expertise. Its study also explains that Sultan Mahmud Shah I was highly respected and treated with dignity in all spheres of society, according to its study.

Keywords: Historical Sanskrit Poem, Mahmood Beghda

Among the Sultans of Gujarat, Sultan al-bar o Sultan al-bahr (the king of the land and the ocean) Abul Fatah Nasir al-Din nicknamed Sultan Mahmud Shah I (May 25, 1458, to November 23, 1511) is considered to be the most important and powerful sultan. Based on the twelfth chapter (Zikr Jalus Sultan Mahmud Begra Bar Takht Jahanbanio Fatah

Qila Junagadh and Champaner Ba-taeed-e-Rabbani) of the book *Mirat-i-Sikandari* (1611 AD) written by Sikander ibn Muhammad (alias Manjhu ibn-e Akbar), so much attention has been given to the statements about Islamicism, appetite, and the lust of Muzaffari Sultan Mahmud Shah I (1458-1511) that his identity started to be established from them. Not only in the western but also the eastern histories related to the Sultan, these three factors are considered to be the ones that formed the foundations of both his personality and his kingdom. But in the same part of the book, along with the mention of his accession to the throne, there is also this statement:¹

कि सुल्तान दीन-पनाह महमूद शाह बेगदा बरोज़ यक् शुम्बा, शहर शाबान 853 सुल्लत व सुतीन व सुमा नुमाया दर शहरे मुअज्जम अहमदाबाद बर तख्ते सल्लनत क्रदम निहाद । बजलूस मुबारक खुरैश व लाईत गुजरात-रा ज़ेब व ज़ीनत दाद । मुखफ़्फ़ी नुमांद कि सुल्तान बेहतरीने सलातीने गुजरात अस्त चः अज़ मा-त-क्रदम व चः अज़ मा-ताख़िर हम दर कसरत अँदल व हम दर एहतिमाम गज़ा व रिआँयत अहक़ाम इस्लाम व मुसल्मानान् व हम दर सखावत व फ़ुतूत ।

The Defender of the Faith, Mehmud Shah Begda, put his foot on the throne of the Sultanate on Sunday, the first of the glorious month of Shabaan H. 863 (A. C. 18th June 1459) in the great city of Ahmedabad, and by his accession, he conferred grace and luster on the country of Gujarat. ...May it not remain secret that this Sultan was the best of the Gujarat Sultans as a ruler, a warrior, and a dispenser of justice.²

In this chapter, along with the account of his conquests, there are valuable details of his unparalleled achievements as a king, and it is also mentioned that:³

वज्रै व शरीफ़े गुजरात मुल्फ़िक़ बर ईनंद कि मिस्ल सुल्तान महमूद बेगदा बादशाही अज़ बादशाहाने गुजरात न बूदह ।

Great and poor are agreed in this that, among the Sultans of Gujarat either before or after him, there was no one like Mehmud-Begda.⁴

Mirat-i-Sikandari describes the word Begda as:⁵

बाज़ अज़ अह्ने गुजरात वजः तस्त्रीयः बेगदा-रा चुनी नक्ल मीकुनंद कि बेगदा बज़ुबान हिन्दी गावेदा गोईंद कि शाख-हाए चप व रास्त मिस्ल दर दस्त कसे कि बः बग़लगीरी कशादः कुनद बर आमदः बाशद व बरुत-हाए सुल्तान सतबर व दराज़ बुदंद मिस्ल शाख-हाए

¹Mirati Sikandari, p. 71

²ibn-e-Muhammad, nd, pp. 39-40

³ibn-e-Muhammad, nd, p. 76

⁴Mirati Sikandari, nd, p. 45

⁵Mirati Sikandari, nd, p. 71

मङ्कूर दर उर्फ बचुनी लुक्ख शोहरत याफत । बाज मीगोइंद बी बजुवान हिन्दुवान गुजरात अददे दो-रा गोईद व चू सुल्तान दो किला-रा फतह कर्द: बूद यक् जूनागढ़ यक् चाँपानेर अज ई जहत सुल्तान महमूद बेगड़ा गोईद ।

Begda, in the Gujarati language, is the name for a bullock whose horns stretch horizontally forward in the manner of a person extending his arms to embrace another, the mustaches of the Sultan being so thick and long that they resembled the horns of such a bullock. Others say, that Begda is derived from “be” and “gadh”, a castle from the fact of his having taken the two rock fortresses of Junagadhand Champaner; and hence he was called Begda.⁶

Zafar Khan was the founder of Muzaffar Shahi’s independent kingdom of Gujarat. Earlier he had been the governor of Gujarat appointed by the Delhi Sultanate. His title was Muzaffar Khan. After establishing his regime, he took the title of Muzaffar Shah I. He was succeeded by Shamsuddin Muhammad Shah I, Nasiruddin Ahmad Shah I (who founded the city of Ahmedabad), Muhammad Shah II Zar Bakhsh, Qutbuddin Jalal Khan, Muizzuddin Muhammad Shah II, Qutbuddin Ahmad Shah II, Dawood Shah, and then Abul Fatah Nasiruddin Mahmud Shah I Begda.

Muhammad Shah Sani (Second) Zarbakhsh had two sons from two mahals (wives), Jalal Khan and Fatah Khan. After his death, his eldest son, Jalal Khan, became Qutbuddin Ahmad II and occupied the throne in 1451. He was the half-brother of Fatah Khan and was always busy planning to kill him and his mother. Because of this terror, Fatah Khan’s mother, Bibi Mughli (or Bibi Mughalani), took refuge with her son in the house of Bibi Murki. Bibi Mughli and Bibi Murki⁷ were sisters, and the latter was also the wife of Shah Alam, the noble and powerful saint, and murshid of the time, after whose death Shah Alam married Bibi Mughli. Fatah Khan enjoyed the kindness of Shah Alam from his childhood and he also protected him with his spiritual powers on many fronts. Saiyyada Jafar writes:

Sultan Mahmud Begda, the Shah of Gujarat, was known as Fatah Khan in his childhood. At that time, his half-brother Sultan Qutbud-Din was the ruler, and he was looking for ways to kill him. Fatah Khan’s mother took him to her brother-in-law Hazrat Shah Alam’s house. One day, while Shah Alam was teaching Fatah Khan, the sultan came to know about it. He barged into Shah Alam’s residence with the intention of murder. The gatekeeper of the monastery stopped the king. The king said, “Why are you depriving me of the visit to Father Jeev?” Shah Alam heard the conversation and told the gatekeeper to let the king come. Shah Alam said to Fatah Khan, “padhdokre” (read, boy). Now, when the Sultan looked around, he found that a white-bearded

⁶ibn-e-Muhammad, nd, p. 42

⁷Aparna Kpadia has misspelt her name as Bibi Turki

hunchbacked man with white eyebrows was sitting in front of Shah Alam.⁸

Fatah Khan took over the empire as Sultan Mahmud in 1458 when he was thirteen years old.

Muzaffar Shahi Sultans had always shown interest in regional culture and society. Sultan Ahmed Shah I was a patron of knowledge and arts whose fame extended to Hijaz and Egypt. There is a statement about him in *Mirat-i-Sikandari* that from the age of puberty until his death he never missed the Fajr prayer. He was also famous for his generosity, justice, and piety. These qualities were also present in his crown princes. Among them, Sultan Mahmud Shah I was a successful and powerful Sultan, a Sultan who is also praised for cultural tapestry, social tolerance, and linguistic openness.

The fifty-year reign of Sultan Ahmad Shah's grandson Fatah Khan alias Sultan Mahmud Shah Begda is considered the golden age of the development of religious studies in Gujarat. His court was always filled with religious scholars from Arab and other countries. Among the famous scholars who came to Gujarat from Hijaz, Yemen, and Egypt during his reign, Allama Ibn Suwaydis the most notable. Due to his deep knowledge of hadees (hadith), he was conferred the title of Malek-ul-Muhaddeseen by the Sultan.⁹

He also had a Rabat (a building for the accommodation of pilgrims) built in Makkah which was called al-Kanbayatiyah wherein he had arrangements for religious education as well. Wazaif (scholarships) were also arranged for the expenses of boys studying there. It was due to Shah Alam's training that Sultan Mahmud Shah I also took considerable interest in religious affairs.

Wars with the Portuguese resulted in propaganda about Sultan Mahmud. The Portuguese spread fictitious tales about his character. English poet Samuel Butler wrote a long satirical poem "Hudibras" in which he made Sultan Mahmud a subject of ridicule in the light of those Portuguese tales. Here is a part of the verses in which Butler mentions the Sultan's eating habits and lust:

The Prince of Cambay's daily food
Is asp, and basilisk, and toad
Which makes him have so strong a breath
Each night he stinks a queen to death¹⁰

⁸Jafar, 1998, p. 259

⁹Abbasi, 2003, pp. 4-5

¹⁰Butler, 1819, p. 66

However, more recent scholarship in this area has emphasized some of Sultan Mahmud's other accomplishments, which, in addition to debunking such prevailing notions, strengthen the claims made about him and the Deccani Sultans in other Persian sources. It has been noted that in addition to being a great lover of Indian social customs, he was also a key figure in the development of cultural integration, and that any instances of religious intolerance that have been documented in this regard were more of a political nature than religious. In this context, in the recent past, Aparna Kapadia's doctoral thesis (Kapadia, 2010) at the University of London in 2010, and a research paper by Luther Obrock (Obrock, 2018) in 2018 are the sources that present strikingly different images of Mahmud Shah I. These studies conclude that he has always had strong and stable ties with the regional culture and society and that he loved his subjects, and tried his best to foster the all-round development of the empire. He had excellent military and administrative skills too. Manu S Pillai writes that "his violence—which was not unusual for the time—and his religious fervour did not, however, come in the way of efficient administration." (Pillai, 2019) Years before these studies, in addition to *Mirat-i-Sikandari*, Abdul Karim Hamdani in *Tarikh-e-Mahmud Shahi* and Muhammad Qasim Farishta in *Tarikh-e-Ferishta*, and James M. Campbell (author of *History of Gujarat*) have also presented these unique qualities of Mahmud Shah.

The oldest manuscript of *Mirat-i-Sikandari*, held in the National Library of France, Paris, dates back to 1613. Pune's Bharat Itihas Sanshodhak Mandal owns its manuscript dated 1614. Historians of the Gujarat Empire have always used these works as important sources. The Pune manuscript was discovered by Professor M. A. Chaghtai. He writes that:

The *Mirat-i-Sikandari* is generally regarded as a complete and authentic history of the Gujarat Sultanate (806-980 A.H. / 1403-1572 A.D.), which according to the *Mirat-i-Ahmadi* (completed in 1174 A.H.), was composed forty years after the fall of the Sultanate in 980 A.H., i.e., 1020 (1611 A.D.).¹¹ He further states that: "Its (*Mirat-i-Sikandari*) last page has this colophon:"

कुल्बा - हजुल किताब फ़कीर हक़ीर मुर्तजा बिन शैख़ ताहिर बिन मियान ख़ान तमाम शुद
रोज़ जुमा, तारीख़ 3-जमादी जमादुल् अख़िर सन् 1023 हिजरी।

"The most humble Murtaza, son of Shaikh Tahir, son of Mian Khan, wrote this book and completed it on Friday, the 3rd of Jumada II, the year 1023 A. H. / 11th July 1614 A.D."¹²

Along with other sultans of Gujarat, the details of Sultan Mahmud Shah I's deeds are also recorded in this book. In this sense, this book has been a priority in the history of the Sultans of Gujarat for a long time. But,

¹¹A Manuscript of the *Mirat-i-Sikandari*, 1942-1943, p. 127

¹²p. 129

apart from this book, there is also mention of a Sanskrit poetic source (Mahakavya) Rajvinod Mahakavyam which is composed in the praise of Sultan Mahmud Shah I. There are three reasons for the importance of this poetic source. The first is that it was written during Mahmud Shah I's reign by one of his Brahmin court poets, who was also the Malek-ush-Sho'ra of his court. The second reason is that its language is Sanskrit, and the third reason is that this composition also confirms the matters presented concerning Sultan Mahmud in Mirat-i-Sikandari. These three aspects elucidate that Mahmud I was unparalleled in his commitment to nurturing Sanskrit as a state language.

The court of Sultan Mahmud Shah I gave patronage to many Hindu and Muslim scholars, musicians, painters, poets, and astrologers. After the death of Jalal Khan, his widow Rupmati (Rupmanjari) was made the queen of Mahmud's harem. A tomb was also built by him after Rupmati's death. There is ample evidence to believe that like other Deccani Sultans, he also appreciated Sanskrit. The Deccani Sultans rendered unparalleled services in the promotion of Sanskrit between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries. The peculiarity of the development of Sanskrit in these times was that it was used as a political force instead of a religious language. Muzaffar Shah Sultan also promoted Sanskrit as a language of public communication. According to Aparna Kapadia:

In Gujarat, apart from the chieftains' and sultanate courts, Sanskrit seems to have been in use in other social and religious contexts as well. The prabandha genre of biographies of real and mythological exemplars, such as munificent merchants or divine and earthly kings, continued to be written and circulated in the region throughout the medieval period.¹⁵ Most of these prabandhas were composed in Sanskrit that interacted closely with the regional language... The fact that the Sultan at Ahmedabad was also a patron of Sanskrit scholarship (as Gangadhara mentions while describing his travels and as will be visible in the following chapter) may also be one indicator of the wide use of Sanskrit in the region. Further, Sanskrit inscriptions, including a vast number of prasastis, were widely patronised in Gujarat in the fifteenth century. It is also noteworthy that both the sultans and other prominent people of the region, including merchants, courtiers, and women, patronised the production of inscriptions in Sanskrit as well as in other languages. Persian, Arabic, Sanskrit, and versions of Gujarati were all used for monumental inscriptions in the fifteenth century; many were bilingual or even trilingual and well-known poets and writers were employed to write these.¹³

Muslim nobles and rulers of Gujarat also used Sanskrit books. Samira Sheikh has concluded from the study of these books that this was the

¹³2010, pp. 124-25

period when Gujri was taking shape.(Sheikh, 2010) In the middle of the fifteenth century, Gangadhar, a Sanskrit poet from Vijayanagar, traveled from Dwarika to Ahmedabad to visit Sultan Mahmud's kingdom in Gujarat. He used to demonstrate his knowledge of the language by participating in literary or poetry debates or competitions in different courts. During his travels to Champaner and Ahmedabad, he penned a Sanskrit verse drama DaspratavilasNatakam in nine acts in which the Sultan (Ahmad Shah) himself speaks in Sanskrit, but The Muslim soldiers of the army use a language that is neither Sanskrit, nor Persian, nor Prakrit.(Kapadia, 2018, p. 101) The Sanskrit word surtran(protector of the gods) was coined for the sultan and was popular among the sultan's court, nobles, and commoners in Gujarat. Kapadia calls it Gujari in the light of various references and shreds of evidence and writes that on the one hand there was a trend of the abundant use of Sanskrit along with Persian in the Sultani Darbar and the gatherings of the nobles, while, on the other hand, the Gujarati kingdom was also supporting Gujri, and it was also used among the people.(Kapadia, 2010, p. 125)

Mahmud Shah I nurtured the traditions of the linguistic diversity of the Sultanate and patronized them too. There is evidence of the use of Persian, Sanskrit, and Gujri in his court and among his subjects. There are also many examples of medieval linguistic features such as the use of Arabic, Persian, and ancient Gujarati words in Sanskrit. The earliest available inscription of the Gujarat Sultanate which is about Mahmud Begda was carved in Sanskrit. The text of this Dahod inscription dates back to 1488 A.D., and it was created by Udayaraj. This Sanskrit inscription is composed of twenty-six lines that present his genealogy and conquests.

There was a Brahmin named Udayaraj in the Sultan's court who was a scholar of Sanskrit, and a poet whom he bestowed the title of Mahakavi(Poet Laureate). The fact that he was made Malek-ush-Sh'ora also establishes that there were other Sanskrit poets in his court. Udayaraj's Sanskrit epic Rajvinod Mahakavyam has the same status as the Shahnama which was written in praise of Sultan Mahmud. There is only one copy of Rajvinod which was located by Georg Buhler in 1875. It is preserved in the Prince of Wales Museum. The Dahod inscriptions of the Gujarat Sultanate are also preserved in that museum. There is a difference of more or less a hundred years between Rajvinod and Mirati-Sikandari. Parshuram Krishna Gode believes that the Rajvinod would have been composed between 1458 and 1469.¹⁴

Rajvinod Mahakavyam was published by the Rajasthan Oriental Research Institute, Jaipur in 1956 under the editorship of Shri Gopal Narayan Bahura. He contends that Udayaraj composed Dahod inscriptions in 1488, whereas, Rajvinod would have been composed between 1463 and

¹⁴Dates of Udayaraja and Jagaddhara, 1940, p. 104

1469.¹⁵ The Indian printed version would also have remained unknown had Zubair Qureshi¹⁶ and Bharti Shalit¹⁷ not taken the initiative to reintroduce it. It was on account of their efforts that the Shah Wajihuddin Academy of Ahmedabad published its Urdu-Gujarati edition with a comprehensive preface and translation in Gujarati and an introduction and paraphrasing into Urdu in 2012. (Shalit & Quraishi, 2012)

If the composition of the Rajvinod took place between 1463 and 1469, then considering the year of composition of the Dahod inscriptions, this aspect is also clear that Udayaraj remained associated with the Sultan's court for many years, and that the Sultan was an admirer of Sanskrit. Therefore, in terms of the Sultan's daily routines, his conquests, his plans for the management of the empire, etc., the Rajvinod can rightly be considered as important as the Mirat-i-Sikandari. The most important quality of Rajvinod is that it presents the existence of the Sultan in such a way that it appears to be a source of pride not only for Muslims but also for Hindus of his Sultanate.

The sub-title of the Rajvinod is Shri Mahmud Surtran Charitra (The Character/ Characteristics of Sultan Mahmud). It is divided into seven sargas (chapters/cantos). The first canto of the epic contains 29 shlokas (pad), the second has 31, and the remaining five cantos contain 33, 35, 36, and 37 shlokas respectively. The topics of these cantos are presented in the last pad of all the cantos. The main themes include the history of the Muzaffar Shahi Sultanate, Sultan Mahmud, his court, and his achievements.

In the third verse¹⁸ of the first canto (Udayaraj, 1956, p. 1) (the offering of beautiful flowers in the form of this poem is a gift from me to you for your worship) Gopal Narayan writes:

“महमूद की कृपा प्राप्त करने के लिए, संभवतः उसके दरबार में प्रवेश पाने के लिए ही यह काव्य लिखा गया था।”

(p. 7) (This poem was written to gain Mahmud's grace, possibly to gain entry into his court.)

This statement is wrong because when the epic was created, Udayaraj had already been the court poet of Mahmud Shah. But at the same time, Bahura also states that it is a matter of consideration as to why Mahmud, notorious for his religious strictness, patronized a Hindu pandit like Udayaraj. The writer was also well acquainted with Mahmud. Anyhow, whichever point of view is taken, it is evident that Udayaraj remained associated with Mahmud's court as a court poet for more than

¹⁵Rajvinodmahakavyam, 1956, p. 6

¹⁶Former Head of the Department of Persian and Urdu, Gujarat University.

¹⁷A Sanskrit scholar and former Director of B. J. Institute of Learning and Research.

¹⁸अमुष्य राज्ञां परमेश्वरस्य पूजोपहाराय मयोपनीतः ।
कवित्वपुष्पाञ्जलिरिष रम्यः सन्तस्तदामोदभरं भजन्तु ॥ ४ ॥

three decades. As proof of this, one can refer to the text of the Dahod inscriptions. Bahura also believes that Udayaraj remained the court poet of Mahmud for further two decades after composing the Dahod inscriptions.

The Dahod inscription was engraved in Sanskrit by the order of Mahmud Shah I himself under the guidance of his prime minister Imad al-Mulk on the occasion of the construction of the fort of Dudhi Padr (Dahod). The town of Dahod was at a distance of 77 miles northeast of Baroda in the Bombay Presidency at that time. According to the evidence, the engraving of texts on the stone was completed on 16 Vikram Sammat 1545/ Shak Sammat 1410/ 24 April 1488. This evidence also proves that Mahmud Shah I was not only a patron and protector of Sanskrit but also its admirer. This inscription preserved in the Prince of Wales Museum is 3 feet 3 inches long, and 1 foot 7 inches wide. Twenty-two lines are engraved on it. At the beginning of the Dahod inscription, devotion is expressed to the Kashmiri Vasini Devi (a form of Saraswati) in the form of Mangalacharan. Later, while describing Mudaffar Patshah (Sultan Muzaaffar), the lineage of the Sultans of Gujarat has been presented. It is slightly different from the Muzaaffar Shahi lineages in Persian sources, but that is not our concern. Mahmud Shah's conquests up to 1490 have been mentioned here. Thus, the time when the Dahod inscription was completed is more or less thirty years after the beginning of Mahmud Shah's rule, and the epic was created eight to ten years after he acceded to the throne. This also proves that Udayaraj was associated with Mahmud Shah's court for at least three decades or till Mahmud Shah's death on 23 November 1511 or his own death. The selection of Udayaraj for the Dahod inscription also suggests that he had the approval of the Sultan. In this sense, it may also be assumed that Udayaraj would have composed other works besides Rajvinod and Dahod.

There is a sentence at the end of all cantos of the Rajvinod that indicate the theme of that canto. The first line is the same in all cantos:

॥ इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये सु-
रेन्द्रसरस्वतीसम्वादो नाम प्रथमस्सर्गः ॥

Dialogue between Surendra and Saraswati is the first chapter of the RajvinodMahakavya.

॥इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये वं-
शानुसङ्कीर्तनो नाम द्वितीयः सर्गः ॥

Second chapter of the RajvinodMahakavya is called genealogy.

॥इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये सभा-
समागमो नाम तृतीयः सर्गः ॥

The third chapter of the Rajvinodmahakavya is called Assembly.

॥ इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये सर्वा-
वसरो नाम चतुर्थः सर्गः ॥

The fourth canto of the Rajvinodmahakavyais the Moments of Leisure.

॥ इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये **सङ्गी-
तरङ्गप्रसङ्गो** नाम पञ्चमः सर्गः ॥

The fifth canto of the Rajvinodmahakavyais called the Music Fete.

॥ इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये **वि-
जययात्रोत्सवो** नाम षष्ठः सर्गः ॥

Rajvinodmahakavya's sixth canto is called Celebration of Victorious Expeditions.

॥ इति श्रीमहाराजाधिराज-जरबक्सपातसाह-श्रीमहमूदसुरत्राणचरित्रे राजविनोदमहाकाव्ये **वि-
जयलक्ष्मीलाभो** नाम सप्तमः सर्गः ॥

The seventh canto of the composition of Udayaraj, Rajvinodmahakavya, is called Prowess and Goddess of Victory.

In the first canto, there is a dialogue between Saraswati and Indra, in which Saraswatinarrates the greatness of Sultan Mahmud's court. The second canto contains the genealogy of Sultan Mahmud. The third canto is a vivid description of Mahmud's court and his splendor. In the fourth canto, there is an account of the Sultan's assembly in the court. The fifth canto presents the Sultan's interest in music. The sixth canto mentions the Sultan's conquests, and the seventh canto deals with Sultan's noble qualities, kindness, and generosity.

The first part of this Sanskrit poem is written in the form of a dialogue between Indra and Saraswati (Surendra Saraswati Samavad). Brahma's daughter Saraswati leaves her abode for an expedition to the earthly world. Her father orders Indra to search for her. After wandering around the globe for four hundred days, Indra is surprised to see that Saraswati is busy chatting with scholars in Sultan Mahmud's court (temple). Saraswati replies to the queries of Indra from the court of Sultan Mahmud. Poet Udayaraj presents Sultan Mahmud as a Hindu Khatri king, and the protector of Hindus. He says that the court of Sultan Mahmud is more spiritual than the court of Raja Indra. This is the place where Saraswati is living. When Indra inquires reasons for taking refuge here after saying goodbye to the Brahmalo, Saraswati begins praising the Sultan's court, and says that when there is a king like Sultan Mahmud on earth, what will she do in the skies? He has made the earth a paradise for the goddess of knowledge. It is not just a royal court; it is also the abode of scholars. This is the place where poetry is engrossed in the flight of its imagination without any bond, where the river of wisdom and art flows. Not only Indra's, but the sultan's throne is also more shining than the thrones of Vishnu (Kamalapati) and Kama (Rati Vallabh). She believes that there are worlds of music that cannot be found anywhere else.

ब्राह्मि ! ब्रह्मसभां सुभाषितरसत्यागेन रुक्षाननां
कृत्वा क्रीडसि भूतले किमिति सा शक्रेण पृष्टाऽब्रवीत् ।

सुत्रामन् महमूदसाहिनृपतेः विद्याविदां संसदि

स्वच्छन्दप्रसरत्कवित्वलहरीं त्यक्तुं कथं शक्यते ।।११।।

इन्द्रः किं कमलापतिः किमथवा किंवा रतेर्वल्लभः
शृङ्गारः किमु मूर्तिमानिति बुधैस्सोल्लासमालोकितः ।
चञ्चामरवीजितः सुमहच्छत्रेण विभ्राजितः
सोऽयं श्रीमहमूदसाहनृपतिः सिंहासने राजते ॥१२॥

औदार्यं परमस्य शौर्यमतुलं गाम्भीर्यमुख्यान् गुणान्
प्रेक्ष्य श्रीमहमूदसाहनृपतेराश्चर्यमासेदुषाम् ।¹⁹

Saraswati says that she has no intention of returning from there now. The second sarga presents the genealogy of the Gujarati sultans. It begins from Muzaffar Shah who has been called *Suryavanshi* for giving him the Khatri identity. The *Mirat-i-Sikandari* also calls his ancestors Hindu *Tak*. In its second chapter entitled *Zikr Silsila-e Ansaab Aali Intansaab Salateen-e-Gujarat* it is recorded that:²⁰

वज्रै व शरीफे गुजरात मुल्फिक्र बर ईनंद कि मिस्ल सुल्तान महमूद बेगड़ा बादशाही अज़ बादशाहाने गुजरात न बूदह । बाज़ अज़ अह्ले गुजरात वजः तस्त्रीयः बेगड़ा-रा चुनी नक़ल मीकुनंद कि बेगदा बज़ुबान हिन्दी गावेदा गोईंद कि शाख-हाए चप व रास्त मिस्ल दर दस्त कसे कि बः बग़लगीरी कशादः कुनद बर आमदः बाशद व बरुत-हाए सुल्तान सतबर व दराज़ बुदंद मिस्ल शाख-हाए मज़कूर दर उर्फ़ बचुनी लुक्ब शोहरत याफ़त । बाज़ मीगोईंद बी बज़ुबान हिन्दुवान गुजरात अददे दो-रा गोईंद व चूँ सुल्तान दो क़िला-रा फतह कर्दः बूद यक् जूनागढ़ यक् चाँपानेर अज़ ई जहत सुल्तान महमूद बेगड़ा गोईंद ।

The first among the ancestors of the Sultans of Gujarat who became qualified with the honour and distinction of Islam was one Saharan, the Tank. He was styled *Wajih-ul-Mulk* when he became a Muhammadan. “Tank” means expelled from caste. The Tanks were expelled from the caste for wine drinking.²¹

On the contrary, Udayaraj declares Muzaffar Shah as the direct heir of the Khatri and writes that Zafar Khan (Sultan Muhammad bin Zafar Khan) came from Delhi to GurajarDesh (Gujarat) to help Krishna in his battle with Kali. The establishment of his kingdom in Gujarat was a

¹⁹p. 2

²⁰Ibn-e-Muhammad, 1308 H.

²¹ibn-e-Muhammad, nd, p. 1.

Incomplete translation by F. L. Faridi. Complete translation of the Persian text is as follows:

The first person among them who converted to Islam and was characterized by the attribute of faith was Saharan, whose title was *Wajih-ul-Mulk*. The one being referred to is from the nation of Tak. It is written in the historical analects of the Hindus that Tak and Khatri are brothers of each other. One of them who had a penchant for drinking was expelled by the Khatri from their tribe. Such a man is called Takiya in Hindu language. (Hashmi)

divine order, due to which the king of Malwa was saved. Udayaraj calls him Malwarajbandimokch:

मुमोच बन्दीकृतमल्पखानमनल्पवीर्यं बलवत्तरो यः ।
वंश्यास्ततो मालवराजबन्दिमोक्षपदाख्यं बिरुदं वहन्ति ॥५॥²²

Muhammad Shah, the son of Muzaffar Shah, is said to be a person who had immense strength in his arms, and whose existence was radiant like thousands of shining suns (SahastrabhanupratimahaPratapah). His brilliance dispelled the darkness of isolation and poverty from the world:

उदित्वरो यस्य बभौ जगत्यां सहस्रभानुप्रतिमः प्रतापः ।
यो मल्लखानाख्यमुलूकमिन्द्रप्रस्थस्थमुद्वेजितवान् द्विषन्तम् ॥८॥²³

Both bhog and sambhog are important in the Sanskrit traditions of the Mahakavya for demonstrating the king's strength, his mental, physical, and sexual prowess. The same situation exists in this poem. Sultan Mahmud of Udayaraj is not only a supreme example of physical strength and moral values, but he is also the bearer of various responsibilities due to being the deputy of God. While presenting the genealogy of the Sultan, the poet calls him the heir of the Lord of the country of Gurjar i.e., Gujarat (Gurjara Chhamapati), and states that the Sultan himself is a GurjarPatsaha (Gujarati King):

वंशस्सहस्रांशुभवो जगत्यां जागर्त्यसौ राजभिरर्चनीयः ।
कर्णोपमो यत्र किलावतीर्णः श्रीमान् पुरा साहिमुदप्फरेन्द्रः ॥१॥

लीनस्य वाद्धौ कलिकालभीत्या कृष्णस्य साहाय्यचिकीर्षयेव ।
दिल्लीपुराद् गूर्जरदेशमेत्य दधार यो मूर्द्ध्नि सितातपत्रम् ॥२॥²⁴

The Sultan has also been called the Maharajadhiraja (the king of kings). He is such a king over whom no one has authority, whereas, everyone is under his command. That is why the poet repeatedly calls him Chakravarti (the absolute king) who commands the Bharatvarsha. While glorifying the Sultan's role as Chakravarti, the poet glorifies him as a king whom the world bestows when it is at war. Aparna Kapadia believes that this is the last Sanskrit Mahakavya in which a Muslim ruler is portrayed as a Hindu Chakravarti. One of the stanzas of the second canto of Rājavinod can be cited as an example of Udayaraj praising Muhammad, the predecessor of Mahmud Begda:

सूर्यो दिवैव कुरुते जगति प्रकाशं कान्तिं शशी वितनुते नियतं निशायाम् ।
श्रीमन्महम्मदनराधिपतेः पृथिव्यां दृष्टः प्रतापयशसोर्युगपत्प्रचारः ॥१५॥²⁵

²²Udayaraj, p. 4

²³Udayaraj, p. 4

²⁴Udayaraj, p. 3

²⁵Udayaraj, p. 4

The sun illuminates the world only during the day; the moon shines only for the night; where the protection of Muhammad's power and fame is constant in the world.

footnoteTranslation by the author. The author is thankful to Dr. Ashutosh Dwivedi, Department of Sanskrit, Jai Prakash University, Chapra for his assistance in translating the Sanskrit texts.

As elaborated earlier, the court of Mahmud Shah I has been portrayed as a dwelling place for Lakshmi Saraswati. Lakshmi herself resides in him and he never crosses his limits. This description is in the following words:

सौन्दर्ये मकरध्वजप्रतिनिधिं दाने च कर्णोपमं
कारुण्ये रघुनन्दनेन सदृशं भीमेन तुल्यं रणे ।
वाचां सिद्धिषु वाक्पतेः समधिकं लीलासु लक्ष्मीवरं
भर्तारं महमूदसाहमनघं वाञ्छन्ति नित्यं प्रजाः ॥२६ ॥²⁶

(Mahmud Shah I) resembles Makardhwajain beauty and valour,
He is generous like Karan,
Compassionate like Raghunandan, and like Bhima on the battle-
field,
Vakapati in eloquence, charming like Lakshmivara,
His subjects are ready to sacrifice their lives to serve him.

Details of Mahmood's baths, processions, and daily schedule are described in the third chapter, Sabhasamagam. He is referred to as Mahindra (God of the earth) here. His day begins with the sweet melody of the lovely ladies of the harem, and the neighing of the horses. When he awakens, fragrant water is sprayed on his face which resembles the moon in the sea, and the navel's musk (kurangnabhishrikhandkashmiravilipanaha), obtained from Kashmir's hills, is applied to his body. The sultan's mouth is filled with the aroma of betel leaf, and the air is filled with the scent of camphor. His broad chest (vishalwakchasthal) and chaturanga are as if the goddess of wealth has made them her abode:

अलं विशालं नृहरेर्विभाति वक्षःस्थलं श्रीमहमूदसाहेः ।
लक्ष्मीर्यदालिङ्ग्य सदा सहारं मुदा करोति प्रमदाविहारम् ॥१० ॥

अयं भुजाभ्यां स्फुरदङ्गदाभ्यामालिङ्गिताभ्यां चतुरङ्गलक्ष्म्या ।
विराजते श्रीमहमूदसाहिः साम्राज्यमुद्राङ्कितपाणिपद्मः ॥११ ॥²⁷

Following a depiction of his entire physique, his attire, accessories, etc., his appearance in the court is presented. Many kings pay tribute to him while he is seated on the throne, and poets express their love for him in their

²⁶Udayaraj, p. 5

²⁷Udayaraj, p. 7

poems. According to Aparna Kapadia, the most significant aspect of the Mahakavya traditions, along with the finer points of the court, is the depiction of the Sultan's body, his beauty, bravery, and manliness, as well as all other formalities. The main goal of highlighting his physical attributes was to demonstrate his superiority over both his adversaries and his subjects. (2010, p. 190) Along with these facts, his heroism, bravery, strength, and professionalism with weapons were also stated for this purpose. In a similar vein, Udayaraj compares Mahmud to the Khatra gods in terms of bravery while highlighting his limitless power. The fourth chapter mentions those kings who consider it a matter of pride to be present in Mahmud's court. The poet says that his kingdom was like the ancient Vanga Kingdom (Banga kingdom; the oldest kingdom in the Iron Age of present-day Bengal on the banks of the Ganges). He is such a Sultan to whom the offerings are made from the land of the eastern sea where the Ganges acquires a thousand faces. Even the kings of the Pandya Kingdom (Tamil Empire in South India in the 4th century BC) offer him garlands of pearls procured from the oyster shells shaped like the full moon. Like the kings of the south, the king of AngaDesh offers him maidens dressed in different colored clothes and adorned with jewels. The king of Kamrup also pays tribute to him. This is what even Magadhindra (King of Magadha) does. The king of Prayag, where the Ganges and the Yamuna meet, offers holy water in shining, golden vessels, while Mathuradhinatha (King of Mathura) takes pride in being the porter of his palace. Different states send him jewelry, liquor, and beautiful women as gifts.

इन्द्रोऽसि वीर वरुणोऽसि वसुप्रदोऽसि लोकेश्वरोऽप्यसि पुरारिपुरारिमूर्तिः ।
इत्थं हि साहिमहमूदनृपस्य साक्षात् काश्मीरमण्डलपतिस्तनुते प्रशंसाम् ॥२०॥

वीरः स्वयं समिति विद्विषतां निहन्ता प्रख्यातपौरुषमशेषधनुर्द्धरेषु ।
आरोहणे चितविचित्रतुरङ्गमाणां संवाहनाविधिषु सिन्धुपतिं नियुङ्के ॥ २१ ॥²⁸

Like Vishnu (Purari) and Krishna (Murari),
Brave like Varun and Indra.
The King of Kashmir also sings in the praise
of his Majesty Shah Mahmood.
He is a matchless expert in warfare,
The King of Sindh is the keeper of his herd of rare horses.

The fifth part, Sangeetrangprasang, includes a thorough description of the musical performances, dances, songs, and intellectual sermons that took place in the court. Charming maidens with gorgeous eyes like those of a deer dancing to the rhythm of drums enter the lavish rang-mahal, where 400 vibrantly fragrant flowers and the heady scent of oud and

²⁸Udayaraj, p. 10

amber are lingering. The veena, the flute, and the harp are all being played by women, along with the Sultan's fingers on the latter. The music is making peacocks strut their stuff as well. Numerous such singers perform for the courtiers, enthralling them with their captivating tunes. Before going to war, a ritual in the same palace involved worshipping weapons similar to those used by the Khatris.

कलावतीयं मधुरेण गायति स्वरेण संवासितरागमूर्च्छनम् ।
निजं मनो मञ्जुलकांस्यतालजस्वनैरिवोजागरयन्त्यनुक्षणम् ॥१२ ॥

इयं मुखाम्भोरुहसौरभार्थिनी विलासिनीनां मधुपावलिर्मुहुः ।
मनोरमालक्षिषु गीतिषु श्रुतेः करोति हुंकारभरणं पूरणम् ॥१३ ॥²⁹

Along with the song and music, there is also the dance of the chosen ladies, in front of which the splendid court of Indra loses its luster. Amidst all these, the young sultan walks to the throne with the ladies. The enthroned Sultan is like the Rajenchodamani (jewel of the kings' crowns) and like the gods.

Zubair Qureshi has paraphrased some verses of this canto in the following words:³⁰

मृदंग की आवाज़ की आवाज़ के साथ पायल की झनकार से अपने वजूद की ख़बर देती हुई गज़ाला चश्मनाज़ नयनें मौसिकी के शामियाने में हाज़िर होती हैं। कसरे शाही में शश जहत उदू और फूलों की खुशबू इस क्रदर फैली है कि उसने खिड़कियों से निकल कर हवाओं के ज़रीये आसमान तक फ़िज़ा को मुअत्तिर कर दिया है। ताबदार ज़ेवरों से आरास्ता, अपने लिबास में जड़े हुए आबदार मोतियों की किरनों से तारीकियों को छेड़ती हुई शहर की मअज़्ज़ुज़ ख़्वातीन जगमगाते दीपकों से सुल्तान की आरती उतारती हैं। लबों पे तबस्सुम के तीर और अबरू में दशना-ए गम्ज़ा लिए हुए एक तन्वी याने नाज़ुक-मियान् दोशीज़ा, जिसके हाथ पत्तियों की तरह नाज़ुक हैं, कामदेव की कल्पलता बेल की तरह सराअत से रक्कस कर रही है। एक रक्कासा एक ज़रा दम लेने बैठती है तो दूसरी रक्कासा इस फ़न में अपनी महारत दिखाए के लिए बेताब नज़र आती है। यह रक्कासाएँ अभिनय भी करती हैं। कोई कलावती राग गा रही है तो कोई कदम्बक।....

Doe-eyed beautiful and delicate women appear in the canopy of music, announcing their presence with the sound of the mirdang, the jingle of anklets. The royal palace has such a fragrance of oud and flowers that it has inebriated the air and the sky. Adorned with rich jewels, piercing the darkness with the rays of watery pearls strung in their dresses, the noble women of the city perform Sultan's aarti with glittering lamps. A tanvi i.e., a delicate maiden with a smile on her lips, with an amorous glance, and full of coquetry, having hands as delicate as leaves, is dancing as fast as

²⁹Udayaraj, p. 12

³⁰Shalit & Quraishi, pp. 24-25

the creeper of the Paradise. As one dancer sits down to catch her breath, the other looks eager to show her skills. ... The dancers are excellent performers, some sing Kalavati Raag, some Kadambak.³¹

In the sixth chapter of the epic, along with the portrayal of the celebration of victory and Mahmud's strength, the details of the splendor of the royal procession are presented. The events and genealogy of Mahmud as elaborated in this canto are very important. It has rightly been opined that the poet has chosen the subject according to the traditions of his age, and has also got the honor of adding a milestone to the tradition of Sanskrit poetry. (Udayaraj, p. 10) On account of the way this epic portrays Sultan Mahmud as a staunch Hindu king and protector of Hindu religious affairs, Georg Buhler, in his introduction to the Rājavinodin 1875, has called it a "literary comedy". (Udayaraj, p. 1) But in the research that has come to light in the last few years, it has been considered an important documentary about Sultan Mahmud. Besides creating a new image of the Sultan, the influence of Muslim sultans and nobles on the Sanskrit poetic traditions of Gujarat is also highlighted. It is also obvious from this epic that Sanskrit had very beautifully incorporated Islamic traditions and vocabulary. It contains many words which are Arabic or Persian, for example, jarbakspatsah (Zarbaksh Badshah), Sahi Muzfarindar (Shah Muzaffar), Mahmudsah (Mahmud Shah), etc.

Luther Obrock believes (Obrock, 2018, p. 70) that this epic completely refutes the notion that Sanskrit died out in the thirteenth century under Muslim rulers. The fact is that Sanskrit had many opportunities to flourish among the elite and the commoners. It is a different matter that Sanskrit was also following Islamic concepts, texts, and traditions. Moreover, most of the information regarding the Sultan in this epic is corroborated by the Mirat-i-Sikandari and other Persian sources. Obrock rightly asserts that it is a Muslim Mahakavya.

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